

Role of Political Party in consolidating democracy: Bangladesh Perspective

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Submitted: February 18, 2020.

Abstract: Political party is one of the key factors of a stable political system and the democratic government may not be possible in the absence of political party. In Bangladesh, parties have both positive and negative roles in democratic consolidation. In fact, political parties have the image of the paradoxical role. The main objective of the article is to analyze the role of political parties in consolidating democracy in Bangladesh. The study is based on secondary data, i.e. books, journals, newspapers and magazines etc. This study found that the main political parties of Bangladesh partly failed to reach an agreement of arranging credible election and transfer of power and institutionalize democratic institution. Moreover, these party also failed to institutionalize democracy within the party.

Keywords: Political Party, Democratic Consolidation, Bangladesh

1. Introduction

Political parties have been considered as one of the central components to the proper functioning of representative democracy (Jahan, 2014). ‘The political parties created democracy and modern democracy is unthinkable save in terms of the political parties’ (Schattschneider, 1942: 1). Furthermore, strong Political Parties are essential for sustaining democracy. To a certain extent, it is impossible to run a democratic government without the help of political parties as they have quite a lot of important functions to the government. Moreover, a strong political party can make positive contributions to the nationalist and democratic movements. On the other hand, a weak political party, a party fails to strengthen democratic practices within party, constrained

consolidation of democracy (Jahan, 2014a). In Bangladesh, political parties played a significant role in the independence movement as well as in many democratic movements.

2. Methodology

The study is mainly based on secondary data. Secondary data have been collected from relevant literature i.e. books, journals, periodicals, newspapers, online sources, websites, other documents on the democratization process and political parties of Bangladesh. The authors also consulted with a number of academicians, politician and journalist to analyze the role of political parties in democratic consolidation. The qualitative method is used to explain the role of the political party in democratic consolidation.

3. Literature Review

3.1 Democracy

Democracy has its roots in ancient Greece. The word comes from Greek demos (the people) and Kratos (rule). Most of the scholars agree on lexical meaning of democracy “the rule of the people”. Influential for modern politics (with regard to a frequent referencing) is the “Gettysburg Address” of the U.S. president Abraham Lincoln, who coined democracy as a “government of the people, by the people and for the people”. But there is some complexity on the practical meaning of ‘rule’ and lack of consensus on the practical meaning of democracy. Therefore, the debate about democracy has been ongoing for centuries and the debate is constantly developing new understandings, which can be placed into a continuum that ranges from maximalist to minimalist approaches.

The minimalist democratic scholars such as Adam Przeworski, Joseph Schumpeter, Karl Popper, William Riker, and Russel Hardin focuses on the electoral system and they didn’t set any condition for democratic outcomes. According to Przeworski (1999) democracy is “a system in which parties lose elections”. He argues that the essential value of democracy is in the peaceful transfer of power through regular elections. Schumpeter (1950) defines democracy as a method of transferring decision making to individuals who have gained power through a competitive struggle. Huntington like Schumpeter also emphasizes on competitive elections for effective power as the essence of

democracy. Popper (1963) argues that democracies are a system wherein one administration can be replaced by another without bloodshed, which to him indicates elections.

On the other hand, maximalist theorist of democracy argued, without effective guarantees of civil liberties, elections do not constitute democracy, and that a “procedural minimum” for defining democracy must include not only elections but reasonably broad guarantees of basic civil rights - such as freedom of speech, association and assembly. Therefore, maximalist scholars of democracy have identified further characteristics to meaningfully constitute a democracy. Among them, Robert Dahl (1971) mentions three essential conditions for well-functioning multiparty democracy such as a) extensive competition by political candidates and their groups or parties; b) political participation that provides the choice for the electorate to select candidates in free and fair elections; and, c) civil and political liberties that enable citizens to express themselves without fear of punishment. Larry Diamond (1995:11) defines democracy is “not only a civilian, constitutional, multiparty regime, with regular, free and fair elections and universal suffrage, but organizational and informational pluralism; extensive civil liberties (freedom of expression, freedom of the press, freedom to form and join organizations); effective power for elected officials; and functional autonomy for legislative, executive and judicial organs of government”.

Despite the many differences in how democracy is defined above, there are two basic assumptions of democracy, namely, that all people are equal (equality) and that all people are free (liberty). In addition, certain minimum conditions must be met in order for a system to be labelled democratic i.e. respect for human rights and the rule of law; collective deliberation, choice and participation; representative and accountable government. Democracy emphasizes that values should not be forced upon any people, and stipulates liberty, the separation of power, majority rule, and the sovereignty of the people. Democracy gives primacy to the political and moral values of equality, reciprocity, and respect for the views of others.

Nowadays democracy treated as the most notably acceptable way of governance. Regarding democratic values, Peters (1981: 38) says "Democracy is a way of life in which high value is placed on the development of reason and principles such as freedom, truth-telling, impartiality, and respect for persons, which the use of reason in social life presupposes”.

3.2 Political Party

There is no single definition of political parties. A political party can be defined as an organized and presumably durable association, either of individuals or of distinguishable groups of individuals, which endeavours to place its members in governmental offices for the purpose of bringing about the adoption of favoured political policies or programmes. MacIver defines the political party as an “association of organized in support of some principles or policy which by constitutional means it endeavours to make the determinant of government (MacIver, 2013: 396). Huckshorn (1984) says a political party is an autonomous group of citizens having the purpose of making nominations and contesting elections in the hope of gaining control over governmental power through the capture of public offices and the organization of government. Downs (1964) says it is a coalition of men seeking to control the governing apparatus by legal means. Schlesinger (1991) defines a political party as a group organized to gain control of the government in the name of the group by winning election to public office. Aldrich (1995) says that political parties can be seen as coalitions of elites to capture and use political office, but it is more than that. It is an institutionalized coalition, one that has adopted rules, norms and procedures. Leacock says “By a political party we mean, more or less organized group of citizens who act together as a political unit. They share or profess to share the same options on public questions and by exercising their voting power towards a common end, seek to obtain control of the government (Leacock, 1921: 311)” According to Gilchrist (1921:327) “A political party may be defined as an organized group of citizens who profess to share the same political views and who, by acting as a political unit try to control the government.” Andrew Heywood (2002:222) says, “a political party is a group of people that is organised for the purpose of winning government power, by electoral or other means”. Parties are often confused with interest groups or social movements. Political parties may seek political power through elections or revolutions.

According to article 152 of the Constitution of Bangladesh, political party “includes a group or combination of persons who operate within or outside Parliament under a distinctive name and who hold themselves out for the purpose of propagating a political opinion or engaging in any other political activity”. Additionally, according to political parties’ ordinance 1978, “political party” includes a group or combination of persons who operate under a distinctive name and who hold themselves out for the purpose of propagating any political opinion or engaging in any other political activity”.

Political parties have essential function including aggregating citizen interests, forming a government, developing and promoting policy position and programmes, and grooming and selecting political leadership (Carothers, 2006). The major role of political parties are interested aggregation and articulation, political recruitment and socialization, representation and mobilization, facilitate accountability of government, connect citizens with the government, parties can create political legitimacy for regimes, conciliate and manage conflict among competing groups, facilitate national integration, and promote political stability. In recent years, academics and practitioners of democracy-building projects have heightened the role of political parties in promoting and consolidating democracy (Jahan 2014).

3.3 Consolidating Democracy/Democratic consolidation

Scholars have a different view of democratic consolidation. Schmitter defines the minimalist conception of a consolidated democratic regime as “the process of transforming the accidental arrangements, prudential norms, and contingent solution that has emerged during the transition into relations of cooperation and competition that is reliably known, regularly practised, and voluntarily accepted by those persons or collectives that participate in democratic governance” (Schmitter, 1992:424).

Linz (1990:158) considered consolidated democracy is one in which “none of the major political actors, parties, or organized interests, forces, or institutions consider (s) that there is an alternative to the democratic process to gain power and that no political institutions or groups have a claim to veto the action of democratically elected decision makers. To put it simply democracy must be seen as ‘the only game in town.’” Democratic consolidation is about regime maintenance and about regarding the key political institutions as the only legitimate framework for political contestation and adherence to the democratic rules of the game (Akubu and Yakubu, 2014).

The Building of a consolidated democracy involves in part an affirmation and strengthening of certain institutions, such as the electoral system, revitalized or newly created parties, judicial independence and respect for human rights, which have created or recreated during the course of the first transition (Valenzuela, 1990:4).

According to Diamond, democratic consolidation means the quality, depth, and authenticity of democracy in its various dimensions has been improved: “political competition becomes fairer, freer, more vigorous and executive; participation and representation broader, more autonomous, and inclusive; civil liberties more comprehensively and rigorously protected; accountability more systematic and transparent” (Diamond, 1995:171). Democracy can be consolidated when it can avoid democratic breakdown and erosion by ‘eliminating, neutralizing, or converting disloyal players’ (Schedler, 1998).

On the other hand, Diamond (1996:7) argues “Democratic consolidation is obstructed by or destroyed causally by the effects of institutional shallowness and Decay. If they are to become consolidated, therefore, electoral democracies must become deeper and more liberal. This will require greater executive (and military) accountability to both the law and the scrutiny of other branches of government, as well as the public, the reduction of barriers to political participation and mobilization by marginalized groups; and more effective protection for the political and civil right of all citizens.

However an influential and widely used definition suggests that consolidated democracy refers to ‘a political regime in which democracy as a complex system of institutions, rules and patterned incentives and disincentives has become, in a phrase “the only game in town”’, behaviorally, attitudinally and constitutionally (Linz and Stepan, 1997:20-24). ‘Behaviorally’ means that that no significant actors attempt to use non-democratic means to obtain their goal; ‘attitudinally’ implies that democratic procedures and institutions are considered by the vast majority to be the preferred way of organizing politics, and ‘constitutionally’ signifies that actors – governmental as well as non-governmental, are subject to the laws and institutions of the democratic process (Linz and Stepan, 1997:6).

3.4 Role of political parties in consolidating democracy

Political parties are the gatekeepers and the measuring political barometer for indicating the degree and effectiveness of the practice of democracy. Political parties, the heart of democracy, are one of the key factors of a stable political system in a country.

According to Philippe Schmitter in the effort to consolidate new or recent democracies ... parties remain dominant in structuring the electoral process, governing and perhaps even in the ‘symbolic integration’ of citizens into the democratic process” (Diamond and Gunther 2001) even though political parties are only one of three generic types of intermediaries between the citizen and the state – parties, interest groups and social movements (Schmitter, 2001). Thomas Carothers argues that efficacious democratic parties do not necessarily emerge out of repeated election unless there are other factors present such a mobilize mass public, civic organization, funds and access to state resources (Carothers, 2006) Larry Diamond, Juan Linz and Seymour Martin Lipset argues that consolidation of democracy depends on at least one party developing their overall institutional strength (coherence, complexity, autonomy and adaptability). Larry Diamond and Marc Plattner emphasize on minority rights and representation (Diamond and Plattner 1994). On the other hand, Donald Horowitz emphasizes the importance of well-designed federalism.

In Crotty’s view “Democratic government is unlikely and may not be possible in the absence of competitive political parties”... ”Orderly government, much less a democratic polity, cannot exist without some form of stabilized party representation” (Crotty, 1993), and more recently Seymour Martin Lipset speaks of “The indispensability of political parties” (Toka, 1997). An interest in the role of political parties is of course not only due to the transition to multi-party democracies but reflects a change in approach in political science more generally. Under various headings, political scientists have taken a renewed interest in the study of formal political institutions, including political parties (Peters, 1999). Certainly, there is a widespread assumption that parties play or can play a crucial role in democratic consolidation.

Without Political Parties’ democracy will never be established and at the same time, Political Parties should have the capacity to represent citizens and the ability to govern for the public good (Norris, 2005). Political Parties perform many functions like; ensure a free, fair and credible election, facilitating the parliamentary government, formulating public policies, promoting public opinion, providing political stability etc (Pakbir, 2018). Generally, a Political Party seeks to influence government policy and for the purpose of winning government power, by nominating their candidates in electoral and other means. Among the stakeholders, political parties are required

to perform an important part as they deploy the candidates for the people to vote and also make sure the government carries out their duties as expected to uphold people's rights.

4. Role of Political Party in consolidating democracy in Bangladesh

In Bangladesh, political parties have the image of a paradoxical role. Political parties have a positive image for their contribution to the nationalist movement, and in restoring democracy in the 1990s. On the other hand, the parties failed to strengthen democratic practices within their own parties as well as the state mechanism. Role of political parties in Bangladesh is puzzling and run counter to theories of political development. Jahan (2014) explains these paradoxical roles of political parties in Bangladesh are discussed below.

First, based on empirical evidence of western liberal democracies, theories of party development say that a two-party system would lead to political stability. But in Bangladesh, two-party system has created political confrontation and instability.

Second, it is evident that the organization of regular free and fair elections and the rotation of power between parties would institutionalize electoral democracy over time. But in Bangladesh, the two main parties, Awami League and BNP, could never reach and, agreement on basic rules of organizing credible elections acceptable to both sides.

Third, according to institutionalist theorists that spread of party organization structure and partisan identification contribute to greater institutionalization of parties. In Bangladesh, the parties exhibit significant organization weaknesses and factional contestations and conflicts to grab public resources have increased which has led to a high level of intra-party violence.

Finally, the theory of political development argues that organization of regular election and transfer of power between parties as a result of electoral verdicts will eliminate the need for agitational street politics to overthrow regimes. In Bangladesh, agitational street politics demanding the overthrow of an elected government has become an integral part of the opposition party's election campaign.

In light of the functions of political parties, the role of political parties in promoting and consolidating democracy are discussed as follows:

4.1 Movement for a free, fair and credible election

Movements by Political Parties are a key instrument for promoting/ establishing democracy. In 1986, 1988, 1996, and 2008 political parties led by AL and BNP, successfully formed a vibrant movement for conducting credible election for establishing a democratic government. Other different programmes, like the indefinite boycott of Parliament by the all opposition, strikes, street demonstrations, marches have continued until acting party government to resign and formulate a caretaker government to arrange the general election. For instance, recently, the BNP led alliance began a street movement demanding the restoration of the NCG system and refused to participate in any election under the incumbent AL-led government.

4.2 Arrange election

In 1966, AL placed a six-point demand which voiced the opinion of the people of East Pakistan. Out of this six-point programme, the first point focused on establishing the people's rights by formulating a parliamentary form of government through direct election. The first point is the clear reflection of establishing democracy. Actually, the six-point programme is the main charter of emerging Bangladesh as an independent democratic state. So, the political party (AL) played a significant role in promoting democracy. After the independence of Bangladesh in 1971, Bangladesh Awami League (AL), led by Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman, introduced the concept of democracy in Bangladesh through arranging an election with the participation of fourteen political parties. Representation of multi-party in the election process is one of the indicators which demonstrate the presence of democracy in the state.

4.3 Boycott election

However, BNP, one of the major political parties, did not participate in parliamentary election in 1986 because of the election organized by the military ruler. This is the first time BNP demanded the end of the military rule though 27 political parties participated in this election. Furthermore, in the 1988 election, the fourth parliamentary election was boycotted by several major political

parties¹ except seven. The reason for boycotting election was the absence of a fair environment to conduct the election. In fact, political parties were confident that the acting military government would never create an impartial environment to arrange a parliamentary election. In addition, the Sixth parliamentary election was also boycotted by all parties because AL-led opposition political parties claimed that the BNP government had rigged the election process. On the other hand, BNP did not participate in the 10th parliamentary election because the election was arranged by a party government. However, BNP has demanded a caretaker government for creating a free and fair environment. After analyzing the trend of participation of political party in the national election, it can be said that no political can rely on acting party led elections. Free and fair election is the main way to go into the democratic process of any state.

4.4 Initiatives against/ for corruption

For ensuring transparency, the ruling political party enacted the ‘The Right to Information Act 2009’, ‘Whistleblower Protection Act 2011’, and ‘The Money Laundering Prevention Act’. Moreover, UNCAC implementation plan was adopted by the ruling party. In contrast, BNP amended their party constitution by deleting the Section 7 that stated people who are convicted under the President’s Order No. 8, bankrupt, mentally disturbed, and infamous for graft and crimes are not eligible to become a member of the party because it was a threat of Khaleda Zia’s political career (Chowdhury, 2018).

4.5 Submission of the audit report

Political Parties have to submit their financial audited report (audited by a registered CA firm) to the EC by July 31 of every fiscal year (TIB, 2014). However, a report of Transparency International Bangladesh showed that the income and expenditure records are not properly maintained by the Political Parties (TIB, 2009). Actually, parties did not audit their accounts externally though most of the Parties submitted electoral accounting reports to the EC after the

¹Bangladesh Awami League, the Bangladesh Nationalist Party, the Communist Party of Bangladesh, Jamaat-e-Islami Bangladesh, the Bangladesh KrishakSramikAwami League, the National Awami Party (Muzaffar) and the Workers Party of Bangladesh.

2008 election. In this regard, Election Commission launched investigations and took action only in a few cases.

Furthermore, every candidate of election should be submitted income, assets and liabilities, voluntary contribution and its sources, or received as a voluntary contribution from any Political Party, organisation or association, and a copy of the income-tax to the Returning Officer 896. Article 44 (CCC) of the Representation of the People Order (amendment) 2009 also states that expenditure of election and its sources has to submit to the Election Commission within ninety days of the election. However, the Election Commission has not taken effective measure in ensuring the accountability and financial oversight of individual candidates and the political parties. In addition, Political Parties are not willing to follow and practice democratic norms and particularly financial discipline. As of August 2012, the Election Commission has received 21 out of 38 audit reports from the registered Political Parties in due time. The Election Commission has so far not penalized any Political Parties or candidates for breaching the regulations (Global Integrity Report, 2010).

5.6 Source of fund of political parties

The system of public funding for Political Parties is absence. The RPO 2008 stated that the Political Parties can receive donations through cheques from any person, company, group of companies or non-government organization but receiving a grant, fund, donation or gift from any foreign individual or organization is prohibited. Election Commission has limited the number of donations in a year. For instance, Political Parties in a year can receive not more than Tk 0.5 million (equivalent to US\$ 7,143) or services and Tk 2.5 million (US\$ 35,714) or services from individual and company respectively. However, no punitive measure is mentioned if violating the above provisions (TIB, 2009). According to The Political Parties Ordinance 1978, all funds of a Political Party must be maintained and operated through a scheduled bank. Study reveals Political Parties did not receive donations through the party's bank accounts, as required by law, but receive to the account of Party Leader(s). Besides, EC has no mechanism to monitor the financial flow of Parties. In fact, voluntary donations from wealthy individuals and businesses organization for parties is common practice in Bangladesh without any reporting or submission of financial or accounting reports.

5.7 Representation of social diversity

None of the parties has met the RPO guideline of having 33 percent of women in all its committees (Jahan, 2018). The AL has a better record than others. In the top decision-making bodies of the parties, the AL has 25 percent women's representation. AL also has a better record in nominating and getting women elected as MPs from the general seats. However, nearly half of these directly elected MPs are 'proxy' women, inheriting seats from their fathers or husbands. Representation of women in the sub-national level committees is low in all the parties. The representation of religious minorities in top decision-making bodies of parties is poor in all the parties (Jahan, 2018). Businessmen dominate the top decision-making bodies, particularly in the BNP and the JP.

6. Political Party in impeding democracy

6.1 Violate the citizen's political right

In early 1975, AL moved to a single party system which destroys the values of democracy. The party was named *Bangladesh Krishak Shramik Awami League* (BAKSAL). All political parties, including the AL, were dissolved and their members were asked to join the BAKSAL. It is widely recognised that in a democratic country should have followed the following characteristics, such as '---the opportunity to organise and participate fully in the political, economic, and cultural life of society. ---- Citizens in a democracy have not only rights but also the responsibility to participate in political systems that, in turn, protect their rights and freedoms' (Kleain, 2011). So, single party dominant system not only abolish the country's political system but also breaches of citizen's right.

6.2 Control of election and party activities

Bangladesh is ruled by military dictators Major General Ziaur Rahman (1975-1981), General Ershad (1982 -1990). Although both military dictators founded the political party by using state machinery, most notably the intelligence agencies for increasing the political support to legitimate their activities (Jahan, 2018). Actually, the formulation process of the political party followed the top down approach rather than a bottom-up approach where reflection of people demand was not

observed. According to Jahan (2018), ‘Break away groups from existing parties as well as some retired civil-military bureaucrats and technocrats joined their parties’. Nevertheless, army-backed political parties conducted three parliamentary elections with the participation of several political parties. This election was also widely perceived as rigged (Jahan, 2018). Again, the political opposition had to function within strict limits which violate the values of democracy. Though the participation of political parties in the national election shows the way to enter in the democratic process, the election was widely perceived as being engineered by the ruling regime where the opposition parties operated under strict control and elections were held when the country was under Martial Law (Jahan, 2018). In fact, democratic values will never be persisted if the parliamentary election will be conducted under the military regime.

6.3 Erosion of trust to conduct/ arrange election under the ruling party

It already mentioned that major political parties boycotted the parliamentary election conducted in 1986 (BNP), 1988 (AL, BNP), 1996 (AL), and 2014 (BNP) respectively because of demanding a neutral election time government. Surprisingly, political parties especially AL and BNP, change their decision for capturing the state power. For instance, BNP boycotted 1986 and 1988 and 2014’s election for ensuring a fair environment by neutral government/ NCG but they did not want to arrange an election under neutral government/NCG while they were in power in 1996. Actually, the then government manipulates the NCG system by appointing a partisan person as chief justice and chief election commissioner. Accordingly, in 1996 AL started a campaign to institutionalize an NCG system to organize future parliamentary elections. Following the sixth parliament was boycotted by all parties, the AL succeeded in forcing the BNP to accept the NCG system which was institutionalized through the 13th amendment of the constitution. However, the NCG system under which three elections were organized in 1996, 2001 and 2008, was abolished in June 2011 by the 15th amendment of the constitution. The amendment followed a Supreme Court judgment which declared the NCG system as unconstitutional.

7. Role of Political Party in ensuring intra-party democracy

In Bangladesh, there is no law to regulate the internal democratic decision making of Political Parties in Bangladesh (TIB, 2014). However, ensuring intra-party democracy is a major concern for establishing a democratic form of government. RPO mentioned preconditions to registered political parties for ensuring intra-party democracy. In accordance to in RPO (Section 90B) a Political Party, desiring to be registered with the Commission, should have specific provisions in its constitution to elect members of the committees at all levels including members of the central committee and ensure that by the year 2020 at least 33% women members in all committee positions of the party to be fulfilled by women, prohibit formation of affiliated or associated body for the teachers or students of any educational institution, employees or labourers of any financial, commercial or industrial institution or establishment or the members of any other profession, ensure that the nomination of candidates for the parliamentary election be based in consideration of panels prepared by members of the grassroots-based and district committees (TIB, 2014). Furthermore, Jahan (2018) identified six criteria to assess the intra-party democracy of political parties. The six criteria are leadership selection, candidate nomination, policy-setting, representation of social diversity, campaign and party funding and party induced violence.

7.1 Leadership selection

The constitution stipulates that the leadership positions should be elected in the council meetings of all major political parties - AL, BNP, JI, and JP. According to the AL party constitution (Bangladesh Awami League, 2019), the council shall consist of a fixed number of councilors, elected by the District Awami Leagues and different Metropolitan City Awami Leagues at an interval of three years. Though the Awami League made Hasina its president during 1981 National Council and since then she has been heading the party (BDnews24, 2019). AL is followed her leadership last 35 years. Furthermore, the election of the party chief of BNP will be conducted through National Council (BNP, 2019). In reality, since 1983 Begum Khaleda Zia is a president of BNP after the death of founder president, Major Ziaur Rahman (Khan, 2017). JP is established in 1986 and Hossain Mohammad Ershad alone is a president last 30 years. However, two co-chairpersons, Begum Rawshon Ershad and GM Kader, has newly appointed by Ershad. According to JI, Ammer-e-Jamaat will be the president of the National Council and he will be elected with the secret ballots of the members in the national council. The duration of the National Council will be for three years (BJI, 2017). Actually, two persons hold the position of president long time. From

1960 to 2000 and 2000 to 2016, Ghulam Azam and Nizamee hold the position of president respectively (Khan, 2017).

It is observed that major political parties did not practice intra-party democracy (Khan, 2017; Jahan, 2018). Furthermore, Councilors delegate their power to the party chiefs to select members of all other bodies. In addition, there has been no challenge to Hasina, Khaleda and Ershad for leadership positions in their respective parties. They have always been elected unopposed and were given the authority by party councils to select other office bearers. However, in all the parties there have been changes in the position of the party's general secretary. There were rival candidates and factions supporting different candidates for the party's number two position. But the fate of these candidates was not decided by votes in party councils. Rather, candidates preferred by the party president/chairman were finally selected.

7.2 Formation of Local Level committee

According to AL party constitution (Bangladesh Awami League, 2019), councillor of District Awami Leagues and different Metropolitan City Awami Leagues will be elected but if any District or Metropolitan City Awami League for any reason fails to hold an election within the fixed dates, fixed by the Bangladesh Awami League Executive Committee to nominate a specified number of councillor. All power goes to the executive committee. There is no scope to establish an intra-party democracy. In reality, the direct or indirect election system is fully absent in making the local level committee which is formed by the decision of the central level committee.

According to the party constitution of BNP, local level committees (union ward executive committee, municipality executive committee, Upazila executive committee etc.) will be formulated through the election. The tenure of these local committees will be two years. In addition, local level committee of JI (BJI, 2007) will be formulated through election as AL and BNP. Like AL, BNP and JI did not conduct an election for the formulating of the local level committee.

7.3 Candidate nomination for National Election

Of the four major political parties (AL, BNP, JI, JP), the AL and the JI made some effort to follow the Representation of the People's Order (RPO) guidelines during the 2008 parliamentary elections to get the grassroots committees of the parties to prepare a panel of nominees for each constituency (Jahan, 2018). In the AL in most cases, the recommended nominees of grassroots committees prevailed. However, in some cases, the AL ignored the panel nominated by the grassroots committees. The BNP, on the other hand, made no effort to get nominations from grassroots committees. Instead, seven special teams were formed under the leadership of the National Standing Committee (NSC) of the party to collect information from the grassroots and prepare a list of potential candidates before the 2008 parliamentary elections.

8. Conclusion

In Bangladesh, both the ruling opposition political party played a crucial role to arrange election which is the gateway of the democratic system of government. In some cases, at the election time, political parties were united for making their movement stronger against the ruling party. In contrast, boycott the election by political parties would be another symbol of establishing democracy. In 1986, BNP, in 1988 many political parties and in 1995 all parties as well as in 2014 BNP did not participate in the parliamentary election. In fact, the democratic form of government always expects the participation of all parties. It already well established that movement such as strikes, street demonstration, marches, press conference, seminar, of political parties is common to ensure a free, fair and credible election. The absolute power of the political party destroys the democratic values which evidently observed in the process of BAKSHAL formation. Simultaneously, the military government formed the political party and ruled the state by using their absolute power. History said election conducted by army-backed political parties was rigged and violated the value of democracy as well. Unfortunately, till now, a political party did not achieve the people's trust to conduct a free, fair election.

It is almost common for all political parties in Bangladesh that they sacrificed themselves for ensuring democracy for capturing the state power but completely silent to established democracy at the intraparty level. Almost all political party's local level committee is formed unanimously by the decision of the central committee. Furthermore, there is no competitive process to elect a party leader. For this reason, the leader of major political parties holds the position for more than 30

years. It can be mentioned that stop corruption is the prime commitment of all political parties, though the reflection of commitment mostly found in passing the law and harassing the opposition party member. Furthermore, political parties did not audit their financial transaction internally and externally (professional audit company). Regarding the source of fund of political parties is not monitored by the Election Commission. Actually, there is no monitoring mechanism. In addition, the representation of social diversity is partially observed at the national level committee of political parties. Though political party, theoretically, is the gatekeeper for the effectiveness of the practice of democracy, in Bangladesh political party mostly failed to consolidate democratic practice within the party and state system as well.

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